

MDM2 gene Insights: InSilico Analysis with Advanced Computational Explorations of Structure and Functions

Rafia Waseem¹, Hafiz Muhammad Haseeb Khaliq²

¹*Centre for Applied Molecular Biology (CAMB), University of the Punjab, Lahore*

²*K.A.M. School of Life Sciences, Forman Christian College (A Chartered University) Lahore*

Conflict of Interest: None

ABSTRACT

This bioinformatics study analyzed the mouse double minute 2 homolog (MDM2) gene, which is known to encode an oncoprotein that negatively regulates the tumor suppressor p53 in humans. The coding sequence of the MDM2 gene was retrieved from NCBI and used to design full-length PCR primers with suitable restriction enzyme sites for subcloning. Various tools from ExPASy like ProtParam, ProtScale, PeptideCutter and Translate were utilized to characterize the physicochemical properties, amino acid composition and proteolytic cleavage sites of the encoded MDM2 protein. Homologous MDM2 sequences from other species were identified through UniProt BLAST. Multiple sequence alignment revealed conserved domains responsible for key functions. A three-dimensional protein structure model of MDM2 was generated using SWISS-MODEL based on template selection and model building. Results from different in silico analyses provided insights into the regulation of MDM2 expression and its crucial role in disrupting the p53 pathway, thus contributing to oncogenesis. This comprehensive bioinformatics study facilitated structural and functional understanding of MDM2.

KEY WORDS: Computational Analysis, MDM2 gene, Bioinformatics, p53

INTRODUCTION

Bioinformatics, as related to genetics and genomics, is a scientific sub discipline that involves using computer technology to collect, store, analyze and disseminate biological data and information, such as DNA and amino acid sequences or annotations about those sequences. Bioinformatics is a field of computational science that has to do with the analysis of sequences of biological molecules. It usually refers to genes, DNA, RNA, or protein, and is particularly useful in comparing genes and other sequences in proteins and other sequences within an organism or between organisms, looking at evolutionary relationships between organisms, and using the patterns that exist across DNA and protein sequences to figure out what their function is. You can think about bioinformatics as essentially the linguistics part of genetics. That is, the linguistics people are looking at patterns in language, and that's what bioinformatics people do--looking for patterns within sequences of DNA or protein.

MDM2 is an important negative regulator of the p53 tumor suppressor. In humans, the MDM2 gene (also known as HDM2) is located on chromosome 12. Most frequently expresses a 491 amino acid residue protein. MDM2 is amplified at an overall frequency of 7% in human cancers and at a higher frequency within soft tissue sarcomas, osteosarcomas, and esophageal carcinomas. Loss of p53

tumor suppressor function is critical for many cancers and is achieved by mutation in ~50% of tumors, but may occur through additional mechanisms. MDM2 is an E3 ubiquitin ligase whose Primary function is to inhibit p53 activity by impeding p53 transcriptional activity, promoting nuclear export, and inducing p53 degradation (Zhang, et al., 2005). Gene amplification (amp) represents a mechanism for cancer cells to upregulate expression of critical cancer related genes and can serve as a predictive biomarker for targeted therapies (Tirunagaru et al., 2021).

The MDM2 protein level is positively regulated by p53, while MDM2 negatively mediates p53 and activity through an auto-regulatory feedback loop (Freedman et al., 2020). In addition, MDM2 acts as an oncogene and plays a regulatory role by interacting with other tumor-related genes, which are inevitable for cell-cycle control. Similar to MDM2, the vast majority of proteins with RING domains are E3 ubiquitin ligases. Other RING domain E3 ubiquitin ligases that target p53 are COP1, Pirh2, and MSL2. (Mendoza M, et al., 2014).

The p53 protein is a central safeguard that protects cells against genome instability and malignant transformation. Mutated TP53 (the gene encoding p53) is implicated in many human cancers, but the majority of neuroblastomas have wild type p53 with intact transcriptional function (Zafar, et al., 2021). In fact, the TP53 mutation rate does not exceed 1–2% in neuroblastomas (However, overexpression of the murine double minute 2 (MDM2) gene in neuroblastoma is relatively common, and leads to inhibition of p53 (Taverna, et al., 2022).

Mouse double minute 2 homolog (MDM2) oncogene is as an inhibitor of the tumor-suppressive effects of p53, that acts as regulator of the stability and activity of p53 protein by E3-ubiquitin ligase activity (Schon, et al., 2002). When overexpressed in neoplastic cells, this gene promotes cell survival and cell cycle progression (Taverna, et al., 2022). In addition, MDM2 is a negative regulator of RB and can inhibit its growth regulatory capacity (Sdek, et al., 2005).

In human cancers, MDM2 expression is frequently upregulated through gene amplification, but also by enhanced transcription/translation in non-amplified tumours (Oliner et al. 1992, Momand et al. 2012). Several polymorphisms in the MDM2 promoters have been found to influence MDM2 expression levels by modulating transcription factor binding affinities and also to be associated with cancer risk. (Bond et al. 2004).

METHODOLOGY:

Tools Description:

NCBI: The National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) provides a large suite of online resources for biological information and data, including the GenBank® nucleic acid sequence database.

NCBI Primer BLAST: Primer-BLAST is a tool for finding specific primers. Finding primers specific to your PCR template (using Primer3 and BLAST). Primer-BLAST allows users to design new target-specific primers in one step as well as to check the specificity of pre-existing primers. Primer-BLAST also supports placing primers based on exon/intron locations and excluding single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) sites in primers.

ExpASy: ExpASy, the Expert Protein Analysis System' as proteins were its primary focus. It was the first life science website - and among the 150 very first websites in the world.

Translate Tool: Translate is a tool which allows the translation of a nucleotide (DNA/RNA) sequence to a protein sequence.

Peptide Cutter: PeptideCutter predicts potential cleavage sites cleaved by proteases or chemicals

in a given protein sequence. PeptideCutter returns the query sequence with the possible cleavage sites mapped on it and /or a table of cleavage site positions.

NEBCutter: It is a restriction analysis tool. You can find restriction digestion map of a DNA sequence. This tool will take a DNA sequence and find the large, non-overlapping open reading frames using the E. coli genetic code and the sites for all Type II restriction enzymes that cut the

ProtParam: ProtParam is a tool which allows the computation of various physical and chemical parameters for a given protein stored in Swiss-Prot or TrEMBL or for a user entered protein sequence.

ProtScale: ProtScale allows to compute and represent (in the form of a two-dimensional plot) the profile produced by any amino acid scale on a selected protein. An amino acid scale is defined by a numerical value assigned to each type of amino acid.

Uniprot: UniProt is a freely accessible database of protein sequence and functional information, many entries being derived from genome sequencing projects.

UniProtKB: UniProt Knowledgebase (UniProtKB) is a protein database partially curated by experts, consisting of two sections: UniProtKB/Swiss-Prot (containing reviewed, manually annotated entries) and UniProtKB/TrEMBL (containing unreviewed, automatically annotated entries).

Swiss Model: SWISS-MODEL is a structural bioinformatics web-server dedicated to homology modeling of 3D protein structures. Homology modeling is currently the most accurate method to generate reliable three-dimensional protein structure models and is routinely used in many practical applications. Three tightly integrated components are:

1. The SWISS-MODEL pipeline – a suite of software tools and databases for automated protein structure modelling.
2. The SWISS-MODEL Workspace – a web-based graphical user workbench.
3. The SWISS-MODEL Repository – a continuously updated database of homology models for a set of model organism proteomes of high biomedical interest.

PROCEDURE:

Download coding sequence of desired gene from NCBI (Coding Sequence of MDM2 gene for Homo sapiens):

The screenshot displays the NCBI GenBank interface for the MDM2 mRNA sequence (GenBank: GQ848196.1). The page title is "Homo sapiens MDM2 (MDM2) mRNA, complete cds, alternatively spliced". The sequence is 1401 bp long, linear, and was submitted on 04-OCT-2009. The authors are Zhang, G., Zhang, Z., and Liang, A. The sequence is available in FASTA format. A dropdown menu is open, showing options to download the coding sequences in FASTA format. The menu options are: Complete Record, Coding Sequences (selected), and Gene Features. The download features section shows the format as FASTA Nucleotide and a Create File button. The page also includes a section for articles about the MDM2 gene and reference sequence information.

GGATCCATGGTGAGGAGCAGGCAAATATGGTGAGGAGC
AGGCAAATGTGCAATACCAACATGTCTGTACCTACTGATGGTGC
TGTAACCACCTCACAGATTCCAGCTTCGGAACAAGAGACCCTG
GTTAGACCAAAGCCATTGCTTTTGAAGTTATTAAGTCTGTTGG
TGCACAAAAAGACACTTATACTATGAAAGAGGTTCTTTTTTATC
TTGGCCAGTATATTATGACTAAACGATTATATGATGAGAAGCA
ACAACATATTGTATATTGTTCAAATGATCTTCTAGGAGTTTGTTT
GGCGTGCCAAGCTTCTCTGTGAAAGAGCACAGGAAAATATATA
CCATGATCTACAGGAACCTGGTAGTAGTCAATCAGCAGGAATC
ATCGGACTCAGGTACATCTGTGAGTGAGAACAGGTGTCACCTT
GAAGGTGGGAGTGATCAAAGGACCTTGTACAAGAGCTTCAGG
AAGAGAAACCTTCATCTTCACATTTGGTTTCTAGACCATCTACC
TCATCTAGAAGGAGAGCAATTAGTGAGACAGAAGAAAATTCAG
ATGAATTATCTGGTGAACGACAAAGAAAACGCCACAAATCTGA
TAGTATTTCCCTTTCCCTTGTGATGAAAGCCTGGCTCTGTGTGTAAT
AAGGGAGATATGTTGTGAAAGAAGCAGTAGCAGTGAATCTACA
GGGACGCCATCGAATCCGGATCTTGATGCTGGTGTAAAGTGAAC
ATTCAGGTGATTGGTTGGATCAGGATTCAGTTTCAGATCAGTTT
AGTGTAGAATTTGAAGTTGAATCTCTCGACTCAGAAGATTATAG
CCTTAGTGAAGAAGGACAAGAACTCTCAGATGAAGATGATGAG
GTATATCAAGTACTGTGTATCAGGCAGGGGAGAGTGATACAG
ATTCATTTGAAGAAGATCCTGAAATTTCCCTTAGCTGACTATTGG
AAATGCACTTCATGCAATGAAATGAATCCCCCCTTCCATCACA
TTGCAACAGATGTTGGGCCCTTCGTGAGAATTGGCTTCCCTGAAG
ATAAAGGGAAAGATAAAGGGGAAATCTCTGAGAAAGCCAAAC
TGGAAAACCAACACAAGCTGAAGAGGGCTTTGATGTTCCCTGA
TTGTAAAAAAACTATAGTGAATGATTCCAGAGAGTCATGTGTTG
AGGAAAATGATGATAAAATTACACAAGCTTCACAATCACAAGA
AAGTGAAGACTATTCTCAGCCATCAACTTCTAGTAGCATTATTT
ATAGCAGCCAAGAAGATGTGAAAGAGTTTGAAAGGGAAGAAA
CCCAAGACAAAGAAGAGAGTGTGGAATCTAGTTTGCCCTTAA
TGCCATTGAACCTTGTGTGATTTGTCAAGGTCGACCTAAAAATG
GTTGCATTGTCCATGGCAAACAGGACATCTTATGGCCTGCTTT
ACATGTGCAAAGAAGCTAAAGAAAAGGAATAAGCCCTGCCAG
TATGTAGACAACCAATTCAAATGATTGTGCTAACTTATTTCCCC
TAGCTAGGGGAAATAAGTTAGCACAATCCTATAG

*pink = Restriction enzyme sequences

*yellow = Forward and reverse primers

Design full length primers using NCBI Primer BLAST.

Primers Sequence:

Product length = 1494

Forward primer ATGGTGAGGAGCAGGCAAAT

Reverse primer CTAGGGGAAATAAGTTAGCACAATC

Select suitable vector:

Perform Restriction analysis using NEB cutter and add Restriction Enzymes with the primers.

The screenshot shows the NEBcutter V2.0 web interface. At the top, it says "NEBcutter V2.0" and "Try the updated NEBcutter V3.0". Below this, there are fields for "Local sequence file" (Choose file / No file chosen) and "GenBank number" (Browse GenBank). A text area contains a DNA sequence:


```

    GAGGAAATGATGATAAAATACACAAGCTTCACAATCACAGAAAGTGAAGACTATTTTCAGCCATCAA
    CTTCATADTACATATTTATAGTCCCAABAADATGTAAGAAAGTTGAAAGGAAAGAAACCCAAACAA
    AGAAGAGAGTGTGGAAATCAGTTGCCCTTAATGCCATTTGAACCTTTGTGTGATTTGTCAAGGTCGACT
    AAAAAATGTTGATTTGCTTCCATGCAAAACAGGACACTTATGACCTGCTTACATGTCGAAAGAACTAA
    AGAAAGGAAATAGCCCTCCAGATATGACACAACCAATCAAATGATTGTGCTAACTTATTTCCCTA
    G
    
```

 The interface includes several options:

- Standard sequences:** # Plasmid vectors, # Viral + phage.
- Enzymes to use:**
 - NEB enzymes
 - All commercially available specificities
 - All specificities
 - All - defined oligonucleotide sequences
 - Only defined oligonucleotide sequences [define oligos]
- The sequence is:** Linear, Circular.
- Minimum ORF length to display:** 100 a.a.
- Name of sequence:** (optional)
- Earlier projects:** Note: Your earlier projects will be deleted 2 days after they were last accessed. You need to have cookies enabled in your browser for this feature to work. [Disable NEBcutter cookies] [Delete projects]

Enzymes that don't cut

1clGQ848196.1 cds

Number of cuts =

#	Enzyme	Specificity
1	AatII	G _↓ ACGT _↑ C
2	Acc65I	G _↓ GTAC _↑ C
3	AciI	C _↓ CG _↑ C
4	AclI	AA _↓ CG _↑ TT
5	AfeI	AGC _↓ GCT
6	AflIII	C _↓ TTAA _↑ G
7	AgeI	A _↓ CCGG _↑ T
8	AhdI	GACNN _↓ N _↑ NNGTC
9	AleI	CACNN _↓ N _↑ NNGTGC
10	AlwNI	CAG _↓ NNN _↑ CTG
11	ApaLI	G _↓ TGCA _↑ C
12	AscI	GG _↓ CGCG _↑ CC
13	AseI	AT _↓ TA _↑ AT
14	AsiSI	GCG _↓ AT _↑ CGC
15	AvaI	C _↓ YCGR _↑ G
16	AvrII	C _↓ CTAG _↑ G
17	BamHI	G _↓ GATC _↑ C
18	BanI	G _↓ GYRC _↑ C
19	BbvCI	CC _↓ TCA _↑ GC
20	BceAI	ACGGC(N) ₁₂ ↓NN _↑
21	BcgI	↓NN _↑ (N) ₁₀ CGA(N) ₆ TGC(N) ₁₀ ↓NN _↑
22	BciVI	GTATCC(N) ₅ ↓N _↑
23	BfuAI	ACCTGCNNNN _↓ NNNN _↑
24	BglI	GCCN _↓ NNN _↑ NGGC
25	BglIII	A _↓ GATC _↑ T
26	BlpI	GC _↓ TNA _↑ GC
27	BmgBI	CAC _↓ GTC
28	BmtI	G _↓ CTAG _↑ C
29	BpmI	CTGGAG(N) ₁₄ ↓NN _↑
30	BpuEI	CTTGAG(N) ₁₄ ↓NN _↑
31	BsaAI	YAC _↓ GTR

BamH1	GGATCC
EcoRV	CTATAG

Open ProtParam from ExPASy and add amino acid sequence in it. Study Physicochemical Properties at ProtParam tool

Number of amino acids: 497

Molecular weight: 55990.80

Theoretical pI: 4.64

Amino Acid Composition (%):

Total number of negatively charged residues (Asp + Glu): 92

Total number of positively charged residues (Arg + Lys):54

Atomic composition:

Formula: C2384H3771N665O834S28

Total number of atoms: 7682

Extinction coefficients:

Extinction coefficients are in units of $M^{-1} cm^{-1}$, at **280 nm** measured in water.

Ext. coefficient 43985

Abs 0.1% (=1 g/l) 0.786, assuming all pairs of Cys residues form cystines

Ext. coefficient 42860

Abs 0.1% (=1 g/l) 0.765, assuming all Cys residues are reduced

Estimated half-life:

The N-terminal of the sequence considered is M (Met).

The estimated half-life is: 30 hours (mammalian reticulocytes, in vitro).

>20 hours (yeast, in vivo).

>10 hours (Escherichia coli, in vivo).

Instability index:

The instability index (II) is computed to be **58.71**

This classifies the protein as unstable.

Aliphatic index: 65.63

Grand average of hydropathicity (GRAVY): -0.786

Add amino acid sequence in protscale tool for studying protein properties especially in graphical form.

Open Uniprot and go to BLAST and add protein or translated sequences of the selected gene i.e. MDM2 gene from NCBI.

Translated sequence of MDM2 gene:

```
MCNTNMSVPTDGAVTTSQIPASEQETLVLFYLGQYIMTKRLYDE
KQQHIVYCSNDLLGDLFGVPSFSVKEHRKIYTMIRNLVVVNQQESSDSGTSVSENRC
HLEGGSDQKDLVQELQEEKPSSSHLVSRPSTSSRRRAISETEENSDELSEGERQRKRHK
SDSISLSFDESLALCVIREICCERSSSSESTGTSPNPDL DAGVSEHSGDWLDQDSVSD
QFSVEFEVESLDESDYSLSEEGQELSDEDEDEVYQVTVYQAGESDTSFEEDPEISLAD
YWKCTSCNEMNPPLPSHCNRCWALRENWLPEDKGKDKGEISEKAKLENSTQAEEGFDV
PDCKKTIVNDSRESCVEENDDKITQASQSQESDYFQPSTSSSIIYSCQEDVKEFERE
ETQDKESVESLPLNAIEPCVICQGRPKNGCIVHGKTGHLMACFTCAKCLKRKNKPC
PVC RQPIQMIVLTYFP
```

Transcriptional Silencing of < (Int J Mol Sci. 2022)
 The <-MDM2</> and <-CDKN2A</> Copy-number-variation Influence [Anticancer Res. 2022]
 [Diagnostic value of MDM2 RNA in situ hybridization | (Zhonghua Bing Li Xue Za Zhi. 2...)]
 See all...

Reference sequence information
 RefSeq alternative splicing
 See 9 reference mRNA sequence splice variants for the MDM2 gene.

```

1..1401
/gene="MDM2"
/feature="alternatively spliced"
/codon_start=1
/product="MDM2"
/protein_id="ACX31156.1"
/translation="MCNTNHSVPTDGAVTTSQIPASEQETLVLFLYLGQYIHKRLYDE
KQQHLYVCSNDLLGDLFGVPSFSVKEHKKIYTHIYRNLVWVWQESSDSGTSVSENRK
HLEGGSDQKDLVQELQEKPSSSHLSRPTSSRRRAISETEENSDELSEGERQRKRHK
SDSISLSFDES LALCVIREICCCRSSSSSESTGTPSNPDLDAVSEHSGDHLDDQSVSD
QFSVEFEVSLDSEYSLSEEGQELSDDEDEYVQVTVYQAGESDTSFEEDPEISLAD
YMKCTSCNEMNPLPSPCHRCWALREHWPEDKGGKGEISEKAKLENSTQAEFGFDV
PDCKKTIWDSRESCVEENDKITAQSQSQSEDFYQPTSSSSIIYSCQEDVKEFERE
ETQDKKEESVSSLPLNATEPCVICQGRPKNGCIVHGKTHGLMACFTCAKLLKRNKPC
PVCRRQPIQIIVLTYFP"
    
```

Add this sequence into BLAST and run BLAST.
Align the resulted sequences.

BLAST
 Find a protein sequence to run BLAST sequence similarity search by UniProt ID (e.g. P05067 or A4_HUMAN or UPI0000000001).

UniProt IDs

OR

Enter one or more sequences (20 max). You may also [load from a text file](#).

```

KQQHLYVCSNDLLGDLFGVPSFSVKEHKKIYTHIYRNLVWVWQESSDSGTSVSENRK
HLEGGSDQKDLVQELQEKPSSSHLSRPTSSRRRAISETEENSDELSEGERQRKRHK
SDSISLSFDES LALCVIREICCCRSSSSSESTGTPSNPDLDAVSEHSGDHLDDQSVSD
QFSVEFEVSLDSEYSLSEEGQELSDDEDEYVQVTVYQAGESDTSFEEDPEISLAD
YMKCTSCNEMNPLPSPCHRCWALREHWPEDKGGKGEISEKAKLENSTQAEFGFDV
PDCKKTIWDSRESCVEENDKITAQSQSQSEDFYQPTSSSSIIYSCQEDVKEFERE
ETQDKKEESVSSLPLNATEPCVICQGRPKNGCIVHGKTHGLMACFTCAKLLKRNKPC
PVCRRQPIQIIVLTYFP
    
```

Result of alignment; we can study different physical and structure properties through this alignment.

BLAST 250 results found in UniProtKB

Overview Taxonomy Hit Distribution Text Output Input Parameters API Request

BLAST Align Map IDs Download Add Resubmit

Accession	Gene	Protein	Organism	Identity	Score
☐ A0A2I2Z0V6	MDM2	E3 ubiquitin-pr...	Gorilla gorilla g...	99.4%	945.263
☐ J3KN53	MDM2	E3 ubiquitin-pr...	Homo sapiens	99.6%	944.11
☐ A0A2R9APP6	MDM2	E3 ubiquitin-pr...	Pan paniscus	99.1%	941.414
☐ A0A2I3SQS3	MDM2	E3 ubiquitin-pr...	Pan troglodytes	99.1%	941.414
☐ A0A2K6DL21	MDM2	E3 ubiquitin-pr...	Macaca nemest...	98.9%	939.102
☐ A0A2K6KDT4	MDM2	E3 ubiquitin-pr...	Rhinopithecus ...	98.9%	939.102

We can also study the phylogenetic tree.

Open Swiss model and add translated MDM2 gene sequence.

Build model and wait for result.

We can change different designs by selecting in the dropdown window.

By zooming in we can study at atomic level and can study bonds as well.

RESULTS

As it is shown in the graph that the protein is serine enriched. Serine is important in metabolism in that it participates in the biosynthesis of purines and pyrimidines. It is the precursor to several amino acids including glycine and cysteine, as well as tryptophan in bacteria. It is also the precursor to numerous other metabolites, including sphingolipids and folate, which is the principal donor of one-carbon fragments in biosynthesis.

DISCUSSION

In the realm of bioinformatics, computer software programs and the internet serve as primary tools. Sequence analysis of DNA and proteins, a fundamental activity, is conducted using various programs and databases accessible on the World Wide Web. The p53 tumor suppressor gene stands out as the most frequently inactivated gene in human malignancies analyzed thus far, with approximately 40% of tumor samples showing inactivation through mutations within the coding region of the open reading frame. Typically, a point mutation occurs in one allele, accompanied by the deletion of the second allele. However, in some instances, the p53 gene retains its wild-type status, yet its protein product undergoes inactivation by viral and cellular oncogene products. The prevalence of these alternative mechanisms of p53 inactivation remains incompletely understood. Notably, one such alternative mechanism involves the overexpression of the cellular oncogene MDM2, as elucidated by Momand et al. in 1998. Further exploration is warranted to comprehensively ascertain the frequency and impact of these diverse mechanisms on p53 function and their implications in various malignancies.

CONCLUSION

Bioinformatics will serve to identify susceptibility genes and illuminate the pathogenic pathways involved in illness, and will therefore provide an opportunity for development of targeted therapy. Recently, potential targets in cancers were identified from gene expression profiles.

The MDM2 gene is a target for transcriptional activation by the p53 tumor suppressor gene product. Previous work has revealed that the mouse MDM2 gene contains two promoters: one is located upstream to the gene and is active in the absence of p53, the other resides within the first intron and requires p53 for transcriptional activity.

REFERENCES

1. Bahceci, D.H., Jordan, R.C.K. & Horvai, A.E. MDM2 Gene Amplification and Expression of MDM2 and CDK4 are Rare in Ossifying Fibroma of Craniofacial Bones. *Head and Neck Pathol* (2022).
2. Bond, G.L., et al., 2004. A single nucleotide polymorphism in the MDM2 promoter attenuates the p53 tumor suppressor pathway and accelerates tumor formation in humans. *Cell*, 119 (5), 591–602.
3. Freedman, D., Wu, L. & Levine, A. Functions of the MDM2 oncoprotein. *CMLS, Cell. Mol. Life Sci.* 55, 96–107 (2020).
4. Lind H, Zienolddiny S, Ekstrøm PO, Skaug V, Haugen A. Association of a functional polymorphism in the promoter of the MDM2 gene with risk of nonsmall cell lung cancer. *International Journal of Cancer*. 2006 08 01;119(3):718-721.
5. Mendoza M, Mandani G, Momand J. The MDM2 gene family. *Biomol Concepts*. 2014 Mar;5(1):9-19. doi: 10.1515/bmc-2013-0027. PMID: 25372739; PMCID: PMC4221809.
6. Momand, J., Jung, D., Wilczynski, S., & Niland, J. (2012). The MDM2 gene amplification database. *Nucleic acids research*, 26(15), 3453-3459.
7. Momand, J., et al., 1998. The MDM2 gene amplification database. *Nucleic acids research*, 26 (15), 3453–3459.
8. O. Schon, A. Friedler, M. Bycroft, S.M. Freund, A.R. Fersht Molecular mechanism of the interaction between MDM2 and p53 *J. Mol. Biol.*, 323 (491–501) (2002).
9. Ohmiya N, Taguchi A, Mabuchi N, Itoh A, Hirooka Y, Niwa Y, Goto H. MDM2 Promoter Polymorphism Is Associated With Both an Increased Susceptibility to Gastric Carcinoma and Poor Prognosis. *Journal of Clinical Oncology*. 2006 09 20;24(27):4434-4440
10. Oliner, J.D., et al., 1992. Amplification of a gene encoding a p53-associated protein in human sarcomas. *Nature*, 358 (6381), 80–83.
11. P. Sdek, H. Ying, D.L. Chang, W. Qiu, H. Zheng, R. Touitou, M.J. Allday, Z.X. Xiao MDM2 promotes proteasome-dependent ubiquitin-independent degradation of retinoblastoma protein *Mol. Cell*, 20 (2005), pp. 699-708
12. Taverna, C., Agaimy, A., & Franchi, A. (2022). MDM2 is a useful diagnostic marker for nasopharyngeal carcinoma. *Pathology-Research and Practice*, 236, 153978.
13. Tirunagaru, V. G., Gounder, M. M., Kumar, P. R., Hong, D. S., & Doebele, R. C. (2021). Abstract P210: MDM2 gene amplification as a predictive biomarker for the MDM2 inhibitor milademetan. *Molecular Cancer Therapeutics*, 20(12_Supplement), P210-P210.
14. Zafar, A., Wang, W., Liu, G., Xian, W., McKeon, F., Zhou, J., & Zhang, R. (2021). Targeting the p53-MDM2 pathway for neuroblastoma therapy: Rays of hope. *Cancer Letters*, 496, 16- 29.
15. Zhang X, Miao X, Guo Y, Tan W, Zhou Y, Sun T, Wang Y, Lin D. Genetic polymorphisms in cell cycle regulatory genes MDM2 and TP53 are associated with susceptibility to lung cancer. *Human Mutation*. 2005;27(1):110-117.
16. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nucleotide/>
17. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/tools/primer-blast/>
18. <https://nc2.neb.com/NEBcutter2/>
19. <https://www.expasy.org/>
20. <https://www.expasy.org/resources/swiss-model>
21. <https://web.expasy.org/protparam/>
22. <https://www.uniprot.org/>
23. <https://web.expasy.org/translate/>